

Multi-node scaling potential of monolithic CFET

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Abstract—This paper explores design strategies and Power-Performance-Area (PPA) trade-offs for scaling monolithic Complementary FETs (CFETs) from the A7 to A3 technology nodes. At A7 node, we demonstrate gate and Middle-of-Line (MOL) parasitic capacitance optimization to match N2 node performance. At A5 node, an Omega-gate Forksheet (O-FS) architecture keeps performance at the same level at lower sheet width. At A3 node, asymmetric crystal orientation engineering enhances drive current and supports aggressive area scaling targets.

I. INTRODUCTION

As CMOS technology advances, standard cell height (CH) scaling has been enabled by innovations in transistor architectures, from FinFETs to Nanosheets (NS), outer-wall Forksheet (FS) [1], and ultimately Complementary FETs (CFETs) (Fig. 1). Among CFET proposals [2, 3, 4], the double-row architecture—with shared front-to-back connection (MRW) [5]—offers reduced process complexity and improved scalability. Monolithic CFETs, with common top-bottom gates, provide a relatively practical integration approach, indicating their potential as a viable path to vertical stacking. This work explores double-row monolithic CFET scaling across multiple nodes. At A7 node, we optimize gate parasitic capacitance to match N2 NS performance. At A5 node, we introduce an Omega-gate Forksheet (O-FS) to offset performance loss from active sheet width (W) reduction. Finally, at A3 node, we apply asymmetric crystal orientation engineering to recover drive current and meet performance targets under aggressive scaling.

II. INITIATING CFET SCALING AT A7: BENCHMARKED TO N2 NANOSHEET PERFORMANCE

The N2 Nanosheet node marks the introduction of NS technology in the logic roadmap [6]. Scaling from N2 to A7 node, both CH and contact poly pitch (CPP) are reduced. CPP scaling demands reductions in gate length (L_g), spacer thickness (sp), and contact width (CT) (Table I, II) —introducing performance challenges.

Methodology for PPA Evaluation: To evaluate device PPA, we follow a structured methodology starting with structure emulation in Coventor SEMulator3D (Fig. 2) [7], which is then replicated in Sentaurus Structure Editor (SDE) [8] to model the INVD1 inverter (Fig. 2 a-e). The channel behavior is modeled using the BSIM-CMG compact model (CM), calibrated to drift-diffusion (DD) Technology Computer-Aided Design (TCAD) simulations [9] of a single nanosheet device [6].

Parasitic capacitances and resistances around the channel are extracted through 3D RC simulations using Synopsys Raphael FX [10], based on the SDE structure (Fig. 3). The INVD1 netlist is integrated into a 15-stage ring oscillator (RO) with a fan-out of 3 (FO3), evaluated at the same leakage power per area. The BEOL interconnect lengths correspond to three conditions (0, 0.65 μm , and 1.9 μm) at N2, scaled with $(\text{CPP} \times \text{CH})^{0.5}$ to account for wirelength reduction with area scaling.

Comparative drive strength per Effective Channel Width

(W_{eff}): As shown in Fig. 4 and 5, the effective current from the VDD for one stage of INVD1 (I_{eff}) per W_{eff} of the N2 and A7 devices are comparable. This is due to a balance of opposing factors in the A7 node:

- **Factors that degrade current in A7:** 1 nm shorter L_g leads to degraded subthreshold swing (SS) (Table II). To maintain the same leakage power per area, A7 operates with a reduced I_{on} per W_{eff} ; Reduced CT decreases EPI volume and channel stress; The use of a backside contact introduces higher contact resistance.
- **Factors that improve current in A7:** 1 nm thinner spacer reduces extension resistance.

Capacitance Scaling Challenges and Solutions: Although the A7 node delivers a comparable $I_{\text{eff}}/W_{\text{eff}}$ to N2, it exhibits a higher effective capacitance (C_{eff}) derived from INVD1 delay per W_{eff} . This increase is primarily attributed to the reduced spacer thickness and the reduced W_{eff} . As illustrated in Fig. 4, portions of the parasitic capacitance do not scale proportionally with W_{eff} , leading to a higher $C_{\text{eff}}/W_{\text{eff}}$. To achieve a similar operating frequency, device architecture are optimized to minimize gate parasitic capacitance:

- 1) **Reducing the conductor area facing the gate:** Fig. 2b-Transition from front-side metal contact (MD) to back-side MD. Fig. 2e-Replacing power wall (PWW) with M0 power rail.
- 2) **Minimizing gate area:** Fig. 2c-Transition from two-sheet isolation to one-sheet isolation (more feasible in monolithic CFET than other configurations). Fig. 2d-Reducing gate extension from 12 nm to 9 nm.

Through these optimizations, the A7 monolithic CFET achieves iso-performance with N2 Nanosheet devices.

III. PERFORMANCE BOOSTING AT A5 NODE: OMEGA-GATE FS ARCHITECTURE

Further scaling of CH and sheet width leads to an increased $C_{\text{eff}}/W_{\text{eff}}$ (Fig. 13), primarily due to insufficient parasitic ca-

capacitance reduction at lowered W_{eff} . To enhance performance, ‘wall-last’ FS structure[1] is introduced as a performance booster at the A5 node. The wall-last approach provides crystal template for source/drain (S/D) EPI growth, enhancing channel stress, while a smaller gate extension in FS helps lower parasitic capacitance. We evaluated two wall-last FS options for CFET PPA: a Tri-gate FS and an Omega-gate FS.

Tri-Gate FS: As illustrated in Fig. 6, the Tri-gate FS forms a high-k dielectric layer (1.3nm in this work) adjacent to the wall of the FS during the metal replacement gate (RMG) process. This configuration reduces the coverage of the gate. TCAD simulations indicate that the tri-gate FS delivers lower on-current per width ($I_{\text{on}}/W_{\text{eff}}$) compared to the Gate-All-Around (GAA) architecture (Fig. 7) [1].

Omega-Gate FS: Fig. 8 shows the fabrication flow of a wall-last FS process incorporating a sideways overetch into the wall-cut to form an ‘Omega’ (Ω) shaped gate. The Omega gate improves gate control by wrapping the channel more effectively. As shown in Fig. 9, with a similar W_{eff} , the O-FS outperforms the tri-gate FS by approximately 5% due to the enhanced drive current. Similarly, O-FS outperforms NS by 5%, attributed to a smaller $C_{\text{eff}}/W_{\text{eff}}$ (Fig. 13).

IV. SCALING CFET TO A3 NODE: FURTHER DRIVE STRENGTH BOOST NEEDED

CH Scaling Limits Active Sheet Width: Within the CFET Cell height, multiple structural components contribute to space consumption. As illustrated in Fig. 10 and detailed in Table III, in addition to the active silicon channel, the layout must accommodate gate extension, isolations, and MOL connections. At A3 node, scaling CH to 42nm presents a challenge in maintaining a sufficient active sheet width. As shown in Fig. 11, to preserve adequate sheet width at this node, architectural optimizations are necessary: replacing the power rail wall with M0 power delivery rail, and adopting O-FS structures to minimize gate extension and isolation footprint.

Performance Degradation and Path to Recovery: With aggressive CH scaling in A3 node, the W_{eff} decreases, leading to a further increase in the $C_{\text{eff}}/W_{\text{eff}}$ (Fig. 12, 13). This increased capacitance penalty causes even the A3 O-FS CFET to underperform N2 NS by approximately 10%.

To recover iso-frequency without increasing power density, two strategies can be considered:

- 1) Improving the $I_{\text{eff}}/W_{\text{eff}}$ to compensate for increased $C_{\text{eff}}/W_{\text{eff}}$, for example by optimizing the channel and wafer orientation to enhance carrier mobility.
- 2) Reducing $C_{\text{eff}}/W_{\text{eff}}$ through gate length scaling and reduce channel thickness to maintain SS.

In this work we focus on the first option - boost device driving strength. As shown in Fig. 15, the conventional $\langle\text{channel}\rangle$ / (wafer) orientation for both NMOS and PMOS devices is $\langle 110 \rangle$ / (001). For NMOS, modifying the orientation to $\langle 100 \rangle$ / (001) under tensile channel stress improves I_{on} by 25%. Similarly, for PMOS, shifting to $\langle 111 \rangle$ / (110)

under compressive channel stress provides a comparable 23% gain [11]. The optimized orientations can enhance device frequency by up to 20% (Fig. 14). However, the increased driving current inherently results in a higher power density. To address this, a further reduction in active sheet width may be a viable solution. As shown in Fig. 14, reducing the sheet width to 8nm maintains performance levels. Hybrid orientation for top NMOS and bottom PMOS may require wafer bonding, increasing Middle Dielectric Isolation (MDI) thickness. We evaluated MDI=15nm, 10nm larger than 1-sheet isolation. This increases gate height and brings 3% capacitance penalty (Fig. 14). However, thanks to the largely enhanced drive strength, the device still has N2-level performance.

V. POWER DENSITY EVOLUTION

With continued transistor scaling, the ratio of $W_{\text{eff}}/\text{area}$ increases, resulting in an increased power density. Therefore, the sheet widths are selected with the intention of keeping power density under control. For example, although the A7 M0 power+NS can accommodate a maximum active sheet width of 35nm, we assumed a default width of 21nm to balance performance and thermal constraints. Meanwhile, the M0 Power + O-FS architecture—which supports larger sheet widths—remains valuable for high-performance computing (HPC) applications and flexible sheet-width designs, offering a wide range of design flexibility beyond its capacitance and performance benefits.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work studies monolithic CFET scaling from A7 (CH 69nm) to A3 (CH 42nm), where shrinking CH amplifies the effects of parasitic capacitance and limited active width, impacting overall performance (Fig. 16). We propose optimizations for each node: A7—gate and MOL engineering for N2-level performance; A5—Omega-gate FS for continued scaling at iso-frequency; A3—M0 power and O-FS are needed to ensure sufficient active sheet width, along with hybrid orientation to boost the device driving strength. These strategies enable continued CFET scaling while maintaining iso-performance and offering design flexibility across advanced nodes.

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Fig. 1: Standard cell height scaling from FinFET to CFET. Double-row CFET scaling to A3 requires Omega-gate FS and device current boosters.

Node	CPP (nm)	CH (nm)	MP (nm)	#NS	#Tr	W (nm)
N2	48	132	22	4	6	18
A7	42	69	19	2	3.5	21
A5	42	56	16	2	3.5	16
A3	42	42	12	2	3.5	12

TABLE I: Device assumptions for N2 NS and CFETs across nodes A7, A5 and A3.

Node	CPP/Lg/sp/CT (nm)	I_{on} N/P (nA/nm)	SS_N (mV/dec)	SS_P (mV/dec)
N2	48/15/6/21	792/895	66.1	67.2
A14	45/15/5/20	844/951	66.4	68.3
A7	42/14/5/18	790/876	69.1	69.9

TABLE II: Device parameters, drive current/ W_{eff} , and SS for roadmap devices.

Fig. 2: SDE structure for A7 CFET with Front-side MD, Back-side MD, 1-sheet isolation, Gate extension 9nm and M0 power. SDE structures are aligned with Covertor flow based on virtual Fab capability.

Fig. 3: a. BSIM core calibrated to DD TCAD simulation for single-sheet channel including extension. b. SDE structure input into Raphael FX to simulate parasitics around channel.

Fig. 4: Left y-axis: C_{eff}/W_{eff} and I_{eff}/W_{eff} derived from RO w/o BEOL; Right y-axis: C_{eff} breakdown into channel and parasitic capacitances. Bars are normalized to N2. A7 C_{eff} are recovered by gate parasitic capacitance optimization.

Fig. 5: RO results for N2 and A7 devices are normalized to N2 w/o BEOL. I_{eff} from the V_{DD} rail is plotted against C_{eff} . Power is inferred from I_{eff} , while performance is indicated by the slope of the $I_{eff}-C_{eff}$ curve.

Fig. 6: Gate cross-section of A5 CFET with a. NS; b. Tri-gate FS; c. Omega-gate FS. Upper: DD TCAD simulated structure; lower: SDE structure.

Fig. 7: I_d-V_g curves for A5 NS (W_{eff} 84nm) vs A5 Tri-gate FS (W_{eff} 84.8nm). Simulated for a single sheet using the calibrated CM.

Fig. 8: Process emulation of the CFET with Omega-gate FS in Covertor. a. Wall(last) patterning; b. Wall liner for etch back; c. Wall fill; d. Gate pull and wall liner etch back; e. RMG

Fig. 9: RO results for A5 devices. O-FS based CFET outperforms NS and Tri-gate based CFET 5%.

No.	Region	[nm]	Limiting factors
1	Power wall (half)	4.5	Aspect ratio and tapering angles; Resistance
2	Gate-PWW isolation	5	Spacer defined, spacer material property
3a	Gate extension (left)	9	6nm: high-k+work-function metals; 3nm overlay
3b	Gate extension (left)	5	Etch back of the wall, for GAA structure
4	Active		Fig. 11
5	Gate extension (right)	9	6nm: high-k+work-function metals; 3nm overlay
6	Gate-MRW isolation	5	Spacer defined, spacer material property
7	MRW (half)	6	Aspect ratio and tapering angles
8a	Gate isolation (half)	6	Gate-cut etch aspect ratio
8b	Gate isolation (half)	3	FS wall etch – wall etch back

TABLE III: Process limitation for structural components in CFET structures. 3a: in NS; 3b: in O-FS; 8a: in NS; 8b: in O-FS.

Fig. 12: Part of gate extension and input pin capacitance do not scale from A7 to A3 in CFET nodes, leading to an increased C_{eff}/W_{eff} with scaling.

Fig. 13: Parasitic and channel capacitances of CFET devices from nodes A7 to A3. The O-FS architecture mitigates the capacitance penalty at A5, but its benefit becomes less significant by A3.

Fig. 10: Illustration of a. PWW+NS and b. M0 power+O-FS structures—indicating structural components within the cell height.

Fig. 11: Comparison of sheet width for PWW, M0 power, NS and O-FS combinations. At A3 with a 42nm CH, NS+PWW provides only 3.5nm of active sheet width, whereas the O-FS+M0 power combination can recover it up to a maximum of 14nm.

Fig. 14: RO results for A3 devices. A3 O-FS device with $W=12$ nm underperforms the N2 reference by 10% due to increased C_{eff}/W_{eff} . Optimized crystal orientation boosts performance by 20% but raises power density. Reducing W to 8nm lowers power density. The 8–14nm W range offers design flexibility for HPC applications. Hybrid orientation requires larger MDI, resulting in a 3% increase in C_{eff} .

Fig. 15: $\langle \text{channel} \rangle / (\text{wafer})$ orientation dependent I_{on} per effective gate width from Monte Carlo TCAD simulations [12] using enhanced analytic electron [13] and 6-band k-p hole band structures, evaluated for a single nanosheet without contact resistance. Circles indicate stress values from stress simulations for SiGe (PMOS) and high-P (NMOS) S/D stressors.

Fig. 16: NS based CFET performance degrades when scaling from A7 to A3 due to parasitic capacitance and limited active width. O-FS mitigates parasitic cap in A5, enabling performance alignment. In A3, both O-FS and M0 power are needed to ensure sufficient sheet width, along with enhanced drive strength to offset increased C_{eff}/W_{eff} and maintain performance.

Fig. 17: Active power density evolution. Leakage power density is set to be the same across nodes by V_t shift.